

A 24-sectors direct power control-feedforward neural network method of DFIG integrated to dual-rotor wind turbine

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ABSTRACT

In this work, a 24-sector direct power control (24-sector DPC) of a doubly-fed induction generator (DFIG) based dual-rotor wind turbine (DRWT) is studied. The major disadvantage of the 24-DPC control is the steady-state ripples in reactive and active powers. The use of 24 sectors of rotor flux, a feedforward neural network (FNN) algorithm is proposed to improve traditional 24-sector DPC performance and minimize significantly harmonic distortion (THD) of stator current and reactive/active power ripple. The proposed method is modeled and simulated by using MATLAB/Simulink software under different tests and compared with conventional 24-sector DPC.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The doubly-fed induction generator (DFIG) has many advantages compared to another generator because it is robust and facile to control. The DFIG rotor is connected via a back-to-back converter; the stator is directly linked to the grid. Various techniques for DFIG have been introduced in works of literature [1]-[9]. The direct vector control (DVC) based on intelligent space vector pulse width modulation (SVPWM) is proposed to control DFIG-based classical wind turbine (CWT) [10]. Fuzzy SVPWM reduces the active and reactive powers compared with neural SVPWM of DFIG controlled by neural second-order sliding mode (NSOSMC) [11], [12]. Neural sliding mode control (NSMC) is proposed to control the DFIG using neural SVPWM [13]. The NSMC method is proposed to minimize the harmonic distortion (THD) of stator current [14]. Fuzzy logic and PWM technique are combined to control the DFIG-based CWT [15]. Fuzzy SOSMC (FSOSMC) is proposed to reduce the active and reactive powers ripples of the DFIG using fuzzy SVPWM [16]. A Five-level fuzzy SVPWM technique was proposed to reduce the torque ripple of DFIG [17]. Fuzzy PWM reduces the THD value of stator current compared to neural SVPWM [18]. Intelligence indirect vector control (IVC) of DFIG using a two-level fuzzy SVPWM technique to reduces torque ripple [19]. The four-level neural SVPWM reduces ripples in the reactive power, torque, stator current, and active power compared to the three-level neural SVPWM technique [20]. The DVC control with five-level neural SVPWM reduced the torque ripple and stator current ripple compared to the DVC method using the two-level neural SVPWM technique [21]. The DVC method based on the fuzzy SVPWM technique reduced power ripples compared to

the classical DVC strategy [22]. A hybrid SMC method was proposed to control DFIG, where the sign of SMC controller is replaced by neural algorithm [23]. The DTC method based on fuzzy super-twisting sliding mode (FSTSM) algorithm (DTC-FSTSM) reduced the reactive and active powers compared to the DTC-NSTSM control scheme [24]. The SVPWM technique reduces the harmonic distortion of stator current and torque ripple compared to the traditional PWM strategy of DFIG controlled by the fuzzy SMC method [25].

A DTC method was proposed based on the neural STSM algorithm to minimize the torque and rotor flux ripples of DFIG-based CWT [26]. The five-level fuzzy SVPWM technique minimizes the active and reactive powers ripples compared to the five-level neural SVPWM technique of the DFIG controlled by the neural SOSMC method [27]. A DVC method was proposed to control DFIG using the seven-level SVPWM technique [28]. The DVC method is based on the four-level fuzzy SVPWM technique to regulate the reactive and active powers of the DFIG [29]. The IVC method was proposed to control DFIG using the five-level fuzzy SVPWM technique [30]. DTC method and fuzzy STSM algorithm are combined to minimize the torque and stator current ripples of the DFIG-based CWT [31]. The fuzzy SVPWM technique reduces the THD value of stator current compared to the classical SVPWM technique of DFIG controlled by the fuzzy SOSM method [32]. The neural SOSM method reduces the reactive and active powers ripples compared to the neural SMC control of DFIG [33]. The fuzzy PWM strategy minimizes the torque ripple and the THD value of stator current compared to the classical SVPWM technique of DFIG controlled by the neural SMC control scheme [34]. The DVC control scheme based on the three-level neural SVPWM technique was proposed to control DFIG [35]. DTC control scheme based on artificial neural networks (ANNs) to reduce active and reactive powers ripples of DFIG using the seven-level torque hysteresis comparator [36].

SVPWM technique and adaptive-network-based fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) algorithm are combined to control DFIG using the NSOSMC method [37]. ANFIS-SOSMC method was proposed to regulate the active and reactive powers of DFIG using the seven-level neural SVPWM technique [38]. SMC and ANFIS algorithms are combined to control DFIG [39]. Neural SVPWM reduced the ripples in the torque, active and reactive powers compared to neural PWM of DFIG controlled by the fuzzy SMC method [40]. The DVC control using the seven-level SVPWM and two-level SVPWM technique, where the torque ripple is reduced when using the seven-level SVPWM technique [41]. DVC control was proposed to control the DFIG using seven-level fuzzy SVPWM [42]. The DTC method was proposed to reduce the power ripple of the DFIG using neural proportional-integral (NPI) [43]. DTC technique and ANFIS-STSM algorithm are combined to reduce the torque ripple of DFIG-based CWT [44].

Direct power control (DPC) is a technique for solving both problems that are based on direct torque control (DTC). The DPC control is a simple method compared to field-oriented control (FOC) and easy to implement. The DPC control scheme uses two hysteresis comparators and one switching table, where one hysteresis comparator for reactive power and the other for active power. The DPC control can reduce the ripples of torque, active power, stator flux, and reactive power of the DFIG-based CWT. On the other hand, this strategy was proposed by Nogouchi in 1998 [45]. The classical DPC method uses a two-phase inverter to output a basic voltage vector in one control period to realize the direct control of reactive and active powers on the third harmonic and fundamental plans simultaneously. The DPC is a technique scheme with simplicity, fast response, and independence of DFIG parameters. Various research papers are published on the DPC method of DFIG [46]-[55]. In this paper, we propose to use 24-sectors DPC with neural algorithms to reduce the active and reactive powers of the DFIG-based dual rotor wind turbine (DRWT) systems and compared the obtained simulation results with classical 24-sectors DPC strategy.

2. DUAL-ROTOR WIND TURBINE

Figure 1 represents a block diagram of the DRWT with DFIG. The goal of the DRWT is to increase the torque. DRWT control is very difficult compared to classical wind turbines. DRWT consists of two wind turbines. The first turbine is the main turbine and the second turbine is the auxiliary. The DRWT gives more aerodynamic torque value compared to the classical wind turbine. The torque value of DRWT is the combination of the torque of main and auxiliary turbines.

The main turbine torque equation is given by (1) [56].

$$T_M = \frac{1}{2\lambda_M^3} \cdot A \cdot \rho \cdot \pi \cdot R_A^5 \cdot C_P \cdot \omega_M^2 \quad (1)$$

The auxiliary turbine gives us torque.

$$T_A = \frac{1}{2\lambda_A^3} \cdot A \cdot \rho \cdot \pi \cdot R_A^5 \cdot C_P \cdot \omega_A^2 \quad (2)$$

With λ_A, λ_M : the tip speed ration of the auxiliary and main turbines, R_M, R_A : Blade radius of the main and auxiliary turbines, ρ : the air density and w_A, w_M the mechanical speed of the auxiliary and main turbines. Speed ratios equation of the auxiliary turbines is given (3).

$$\lambda_A = \frac{w_A \cdot R_A}{V_1} \tag{3}$$

Speed ratios equation of the main turbines is given (4).

$$\lambda_M = \frac{w_M \cdot R_M}{V_M} \tag{4}$$

Where, V_M is the speed of the unified wind on main turbine and V_1 is the wind speed on an auxiliary turbine. The total aerodynamic torque as shown by (5).

$$T_{DRWT} = T_T = T_M + T_A \tag{5}$$

Where, T_M is the MT torque, T_A is the AT torque, T_T is the total torque. The wind speed on the main turbine is given (6) [57].

$$V_x = V_1 \left(1 - \frac{1 - \sqrt{(1 - C_T)}}{2} \left(1 + \frac{2 \cdot x}{\sqrt{1 + 4 \cdot x^2}} \right) \right) \tag{6}$$

With V_x : is the velocity of the disturbed wind between rotors at point x and C_T the trust coefficient, which is taken to be 0.9; x : the non-dimensional distance from the auxiliary rotor disk. So, with respect to $x=15$, the value of the V_x close to the main rotor is computable (rotors are located 15 meters apart from each other) [58]. The C_p is given (7).

$$C_p(\lambda, \beta) = \frac{1}{\lambda + 0.08\beta} - \frac{0.035}{\beta^3 + 1} \tag{7}$$

With β is pitch angle.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the DRWT

Figures 2-7 show that the auxiliary wind speed, main wind speed, auxiliary mechanical power, main mechanical power, rotational speed, and total mechanical power (Pt) of DRWP systems respectively. It can be seen that the mechanical power is related to main and auxiliary wind speed.

Figure 2. Wind speed of auxillary turbine

Figure 3. Wind speed of main turbine

Figure 4. Mechanical power of auxillary turbine

Figure 5. Mechanical power of main turbine

Figure 6. Rotational speed

Figure 7. Total mechanical power of DRWP system

3. 24 SECTORS DPC METHOD

DPC is a method with fast response, simplicity, and independence of DFIG parameters [48], [51]. It was first introduced by Nogouchi. In this part, we propose to use 24 sectors of rotor flux. The designed DPC strategy achieves sinusoidal stator current waveform compared to the classical DPC method and FOC command. The 24-DPC command goal is to regulate the active and reactive powers of the DFIG-based DRWT. The 24-DPC, which is designed to minimize active and reactive power oscillations of the DFIG-DRWT, is shown in Figure 8. Figure 9 shows the three-level inverter vectors representations.

Figure 8. 24-DPC system of three-phase DFIG

Figure 9. Three-level inverter vectors representations.

The DPC performances can be ensured by using a switching table that can be seen in Table 1, to select the switching voltage vector. The inverter connected to the DFIG must provide the necessary complementary frequency to maintain a constant stator frequency.

Table 1. Switching table of 24-DPC method

N	2		1		Hq 0		-1		-2	
					Hp					
	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
1	17	22	3	2	0	0	5	13	25	20
2	17	22	3	2	0	0	5	13	25	20
3	23	17	4	3	7	7	6	8	20	26
4	23	17	4	3	7	7	6	8	20	26
5	18	23	11	10	14	14	13	1	26	15
6	18	23	11	10	14	14	13	1	26	15
7	24	18	12	11	0	0	8	2	15	21
8	24	18	12	11	0	0	8	2	15	21
9	19	24	5	4	7	7	1	9	21	16
10	19	24	5	4	7	7	1	9	21	16
11	4	0	2	5	7	1	2	10	16	22
12	4	0	2	5	7	1	2	10	16	22
13	20	25	13	12	0	0	9	3	22	17
14	20	25	13	12	0	0	9	3	22	17
15	26	20	8	13	7	7	10	4	17	23
16	26	20	8	13	7	7	10	4	17	23
17	15	26	1	6	14	14	3	11	23	18
18	15	26	1	6	14	14	3	11	23	18
19	21	15	2	1	0	0	4	12	18	24
20	21	15	2	1	0	0	4	12	18	24
21	16	21	9	8	7	7	11	5	24	19
22	16	21	9	8	7	7	11	5	24	19
23	22	16	10	9	14	14	12	6	19	25
24	22	16	10	9	14	14	12	6	19	25

The magnitude of stator flux, which can be estimated by (8) [26].

$$\begin{cases} \Psi_{s\alpha} = \int_0^t (V_{s\alpha} - R_s i_{s\alpha}) dt \\ \Psi_{s\beta} = \int_0^t (V_{s\beta} - R_s i_{s\beta}) dt \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

The stator flux amplitude is given by (9).

$$\Psi_s = \sqrt{\Psi_{s\alpha}^2 + \Psi_{s\beta}^2} \quad (9)$$

Where (10).

$$|\bar{\Psi}_s| = \frac{|\bar{V}_s|}{\omega_s} \quad (10)$$

The stator flux angle is calculated by (11).

$$\theta_s = \arctan\left(\frac{\Psi_{s\beta}}{\Psi_{s\alpha}}\right) \quad (11)$$

Reactive and active powers is estimated using (12) and (13) [53].

$$P_s = -\frac{3}{2} \frac{L_m}{\sigma L_s L_r} \cdot (V_s \cdot \phi_{r\beta}) \quad (12)$$

$$Q_s = -\frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{V_s}{\sigma L_s} \cdot \phi_{r\beta} - \frac{V_s L_m}{\sigma L_s L_r} \cdot \phi_{r\alpha} \right) \quad (13)$$

Where (14), (15) and (16).

$$\sigma = 1 - \frac{M^2}{L_r L_s} \quad (14)$$

$$\Psi_{s\alpha} = \sigma L_r L_{r\alpha} + \frac{M}{L_s} \Psi_s \tag{15}$$

$$\Psi_{s\beta} = \sigma L_r L_{r\beta} \tag{16}$$

The active and reactive powers can be reformulated by inducing angle λ between the rotor and stator vectors as (17) and (18) [52].

$$P_s = -\frac{3}{2} \frac{L_m}{\sigma L_s L_r} \omega_s |\psi_s| |\psi_r| \sin(\lambda) \tag{17}$$

$$Q_s = -\frac{3}{2} \frac{\omega_s}{\sigma L_s} |\psi_s| \left(\frac{M}{L_r} |\psi_r| \cos(\lambda) |\psi_r| \right) \tag{18}$$

The derivation of the reactive and active powers can given by (19) and (20).

$$\frac{dP_s}{dt} = -\frac{3}{2} \frac{L_m}{\sigma L_s L_r} \omega_s |\psi_s| \frac{d(|\psi_r| \sin(\lambda))}{dt} \tag{19}$$

$$\frac{dQ_s}{dt} = -\frac{3}{2} \frac{M \omega_s}{\sigma L_s} |\psi_s| \left(\frac{d(|\psi_r| \cos(\lambda))}{dt} \right) \tag{20}$$

A two-level hysteresis comparator is used for active error as shown in Figure 10. For stator reactive power error, the hysteresis comparator used is five-level as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 10. Active power hysteresis comparator Figure 11. Reactive power hysteresis comparator

4. DPC-FNN METHOD

The 24-sectors DPC strategy with the FNN algorithm is a robust, simple, and easy command to control the reactive and active power of the DFIG-based DRWP systems. Figure 12 shows the structure of the system implemented with this proposed command. As shown in this figure, we can see that the inverter of the DFIG is directly controlled by the FNN algorithm. In this proposed command, the lookup table of the classical DPC command is replaced by the FNN algorithm. On the other hand, the input of active and reactive powers hysteresis comparators is the errors between the reference and measured active and reactive powers. An FNN algorithm is used to command the inverter of the DFIG and reduce the active and reactive powers.

Figure 12. 24-sectors DPC strategy of three-phase DFIG with the application of FNN algorithm

The structure of the FNN controller is illustrated in Figure 13. The block diagram of layer 1 and layer 2 is shown in Figure 14 and Figure 15 respectively.

Figure 13. Block diagram of the FNN controller

Figure 14. Layer 1

Figure 15. Layer 2

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation results of 24-sectors DPC with the FNN algorithm of the DFIG are compared with the classical 24-sectors DPC strategy. The DFIG used in our study has the following parameters: nominal active power of the stator: $P_{sm}=1.5$ MW, stator voltage: 380/696V, two poles, stator voltage frequency: 50Hz; $R_s=0.012 \Omega$, $R_r=0.021 \Omega$, $L_s=0.0137H$, $L_r=0.0136H$, $L_m=0.0135H$, $J=1000$ kg.m² and $f_i=0.0024$ Nm/s [46], [47].

Figure 16 and Figure 17 show the stator current THD of the DFIG-based DRWP systems obtained using Fast Fourier Transform strategy for 24-sectors DPC control scheme with FNN algorithm (24-sectors DPC-FNN) and classical 24-sectors DPC respectively. It can be observed that the THD is minimized for the 24-sectors DPC-FNN strategy (THD=0.40%) when compared to the classical 24-sectors DPC (THD=0.80%). Table 2 shows the comparative analysis of THD values.

The simulation waveforms of the reference and measured active power of the DFIG-based DRWP system are shown in Figure 18 to compare the performance of the 24-sectors DPC system with the application of the FNN algorithms with the performance of the classical 24-sectors DPC strategy. The active power tracks almost perfectly their reference value (P_{s-ref}). On the other hand, the amplitudes of the oscillations of the active power are smaller and occur in a short period of time in comparison with the oscillations obtained for the 24-sectors DPC strategy that can be seen in Figure 21.

For the 24-sectors DPC-FNN and classical 24-sectors DPC strategy, the reactive power track almost perfectly their reference value as shown in Figure 19. Moreover, the 24-sectors DPC-FNN strategy reduced the reactive power ripple compared to the classical 24-sectors DPC strategy as shown in Figure 22.

The trajectory of the measured magnitude of the stator current is shown in Figure 20. It can be stated that the amplitudes of the stator currents depend on the state of the drive system and the value of the load reactive/active power of the DFIG-based DRWP systems. Also, the 24-sectors DPC-FNN strategy minimized the stator current ripple compared to the classical 24-sectors DPC strategy as shown in Figure 23.

Table 2. Comparative analysis of THD value

	THD (%)	
	24-sectors DPC	24-sectors DPC-FNN
Stator current	0.80	0.40

Figure 16. Spectrum harmonic of stator current (24-sectors DPC)

Figure 17. Spectrum harmonic of stator current (24-sectors DPC-FNN)

Figure 18. Active power: (a) 24-sectors DPC, (b) 24-sectors DPC-FNN

Figure 19. Reactive power: (a) 24-sectors DPC, (b) 24-sectors DPC-FNN

Figure 20. Stator current: (a) 24-sectors DPC, (b) 24-sectors DPC-FNN

(a)

(b)

Figure 21. Zoom in the active power: (a) 24-DPC, (b) 24-sectors DPC-FNN

(a)

(b)

Figure 22. Zoom in the reactive power: (a) 24-sectors DPC, (b) 24-sectors DPC-FNN

Figure 23. Zoom in the stator current: (a) 24-sectors DPC, (b) 24-sectors DPC-FNN

On the other hand, this designed strategy reduced the THD value of current compared to other techniques as shown in Table 3.

		THD (%)
Ref. [59]	DPC	4.88
	VFDPC	4.19
Ref. [60]		3.7
Ref. [60]	FOC	3.7
Ref. [61]	SMC	3.05
Ref. [62]	SOCSM-DTC	0.98
Ref. [63]		0.43
Ref. [64]		0.50
Designed strategies	24 sectors DPC	0.80
	24 sectors DPC-FNN	0.40

6. CONCLUSION

The main objective of this work was to develop a robust DPC strategy of a DFIG integrated into a DRWP system. The basic idea was to use a neural algorithm associated with a 24-sector DPC strategy. Numerical simulations by Matlab software have been developed to test the effectiveness provided by the strategies used. The results of the simulation obtained show well the superiority of the designed strategy (24-sectors DPC-FNN) compared to the conventional one (24-sectors DPC) especially in the attenuation of the fluctuations of the powers supplied and the performances against parametric variations.

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